

Temporal and Spatial Variability of the Soil Macropore Tortuosity of Marshland Soils in Northern Germany as Influenced by Soil Management Including Liming

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Abstract

The soil oxygen diffusion coefficient (D_s) was determined for structured topsoil (0.1 m) and subsoil (0.3 m) samples of a clayey and a silty marshland soil, classified as Haplic Gleysol. The undisturbed soil samples were equilibrated to a soil matric potential equal to -6 kPa, excavated 7, 12, and ≥ 24 months after liming with a double chamber system. No lime, and either limestone (CaCO_3) or quicklime (CaO) was incorporated each in two intensities into the ploughed topsoils at two sampling sites. In combination with the values of the air-filled and total porosities, and with the help of a linear fitting factor, f , measured gas diffusion coefficients were fitted to the Millington-Quirk (MQ) tortuosity model to better match simulated and measured D_s values. Seven months after lime application, the f -values ranged between 0.013 and 0.500, indicating a more tortuous pore systems than predicted by the MQ model ($f = 1$). The f -values increased continuously with time or were highest 12 to ≥ 24 months after CaO application for the topsoils. For each subsoil, the values were in the same order of magnitude after 7 and 12 months and increased ≥ 24 months after lime application. The results show, that the soil macropore tortuosity as reflected by the f -value is highly dynamic at the time and spatial domains. The direct effects of liming on the f -values cannot be determined due to several interactions between liming and biotic, abiotic, and management-induced soil aggregate formation processes. The results indicate that the f -values increased with liming and that lime-induced soil structural changes are not spatially restricted to the topsoil layer where the lime had been applied.

Keywords: arable soil; gas transport; Millington-Quirk; Pore connectivity; diffusivity, lime treatment

Introduction

Soil structure is defined as the spatial arrangement of a vast array of pore sizes and shapes. Structure formation is driven by the aggregation of soil particles through abiotic and biotic processes in interaction with management practice-induced soil alterations such as tillage and liming (Hartge et al., 1984; Horn, 1994). However, abiotic and biotic soil

formation also includes swell–shrink and freeze-thaw cycles, chemical precipitation or dissolution and soil flora, fauna and root growth effects, respectively (Oades, 1993; Six et al., 2004; Rabbi et al., 2018), which are also a function of the climate and the actual weather. Soil structure and the resulting pore systems are highly variable constructs. Liming (i.e., application of quicklime (CaO) and limestone (CaCO₃)) is a soil treatment used to meliorate soils, e.g., to provide optimal conditions for plant root growth (Kirkham et al., 2007) by forming a more favorable soil structure and pore size distribution (Frank et al., 2019).

It is well known that molecular diffusion is the main transport process for gas exchange in soils (Gliński et al., 1985) which is controlled by the gas concentration gradient, $\partial c/\partial x$, (mol m⁻⁴), and by the gas- and temperature-dependent effective diffusion coefficient of the soil, D_s (m² s⁻¹). The process is described by Fick's law in one-dimensional form as:

$$J = -D_s \cdot \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

with the flux, J (mol m⁻² s⁻¹),

D_s can be parameterized at the micrometer-scale (Haas and Horn, 2018), the soil core-scale (Moldrup et al., 2001; Haas et al., 2019; Mordhorst et al., 2017, 2018), and the soil profile scale (Kühne et al., 2012; Maier et al., 2017). For the lab scale are mostly one- and double-chamber (Flühler, 1973; Rolston et al., 2002) experiments applied. The value of D_s in the three-phase system soil depends on the composition of the soil phases (i.e., gaseous, liquid, and solid phase) because the diffusion coefficient of, e.g., oxygen in air (reflecting the gaseous soil phase) is 10,000 times higher than in the liquid soil phase (Gliński et al., 1985; Himmelblau, 1964) and 1,000,000 times higher than in the solid phase as determined by Jost (1960) for some minerals. The soil structure-related flow path lengths and the connectivity of the air-filled pore network is described by the tortuosity, τ . Models such as the one by Millington and Quirk (MQ) (1961) (Eq. 2) are used to estimate τ (Šimůnek et al., 2005).

$$\tau_{MQ} = \theta_a^{7/3} \theta_s^{-2} \quad (2)$$

with air-filled and total porosity θ_a and θ_s (m³ m⁻³), respectively. The MQ model (Eq. 3) is expected to perform well for sandy soils (Šimůnek et al., 2013), since it was derived assuming randomly distributed solid particles of equal size. In natural soils (e.g., agricultural or forest soils) the MQ model may not adequately fit to measured values of D_s as shown by Haas et al. (2020) for two sandy forest soils. The MQ model is implemented in the Hydrus-1D program (Šimůnek et al., 2005) which is widely used to numerically simulate the flow of water, gas, and heat and the transport of solutes in soils using the finite element method. For D_s estimation, τ_{MQ} is assumed to equal the relative diffusion coefficient D_s/D_0 (Eq. 3). D_s/D_0 is often used to present measured D_s values, because the impact of the specific measuring gas is considered by normalization to the molecular diffusion coefficient in air, D_0 , i.e., 2.01·10⁻⁵ m² s⁻¹ for O₂.

$$D_s = D_0 \cdot \tau_{MQ} \quad (3)$$

Haas et al. (2020) introduced a linear fitting factor, f , by replacing τ_{MQ} in Eq. 3 with τ_{MQ}^* , defined as

$$\tau_{MQ}^* = \tau_{MQ} \cdot f \quad (4)$$

They estimated the value of f from D_s -values measured at two sandy forest sites using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. As already described by Haas et al. (2020), the D_s/D_0 values linearly decreases or increases with decreasing or increasing f -values. Results from two forest sites suggest that soil depths- and site-dependent f -values qualitatively reflected soil structural features and that analyzing the f -values could be helpful for a better understanding of the influence of the soil structure on gas transport processes (Haas et al., 2020).

Regarding the marshlands in the coastal region of the federal state Schleswig-Holstein/Germany, the soil development is affected by numerous soil processes such as decalcification, acidification, clay leaching, and mineral weathering (Brümmer and Schroeder, 1968). The natural soil development significantly changed with diking and soil drainage which began in the 13th century (Behre, 2004), leading to typical chronosequences of marshland soils reflecting the varying duration of altered soil formation processes. The chronosequence begins with coastal salt marsh soils classified as Gleyo-Salic Gleysol (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014) and Rohmarsch in accordance with the German soil classification system (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The salt marsh soils at the seaside of the dikes have pH values larger than 7 and a high degree of exchangeable Na^+ and Ca^{2+} saturation due to flooding twice per day (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). Landside of the dikes, the soils are drained, and high groundwater tables result in Gleyic properties. The position of the water table is highly variable, and decreases during the vegetation period (Mansfeldt, 2003). The calcareous marshland soils are classified as “Kalkmarsch” (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) and Calcaric Gleysols (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014), and dominate most of the younger polders at the North Sea coast in Schleswig-Holstein. Such soils are mainly used as arable land and characterized by a high productivity due to high CaCO_3 contents, and a soil structure favorable for plant root growth. The soil decalcification rate of approximately 0.1 m per 100 years is 10-times higher as compared to rates typically found for terrestrial soils and is caused by the oxidation of sulfites (Brümmer and Schroeder, 1968) and the coinciding release of protons. This process results in the formation of decalcified marshland soils, classified as Haplic Gleysols (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014) and “Kleimarsch” (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005) with pH-values typical for the region smaller than 5 (Prange, 1978).

It is the objective of this work to analyze the spatial and temporal dynamics of the macropore tortuosity by determining the f -values (by fitting τ_{MQ}^* to measured values of D_s) at three timepoints after a unique ameliorative lime application for two arable soils typically found in the marshlands of northern Germany. The changes of the sampling site and soil

depth-specific f -values are qualitatively compared to evaluate the effect of CaO (BK) and CaCO₃ (KK) on the soil macropore tortuosity as a function of time. We hypothesized that f -values are a function of the sampling site, soil depth, and sampling time and increase with lime application intensity, due to positive effects of liming on soil structural properties (Frank et al., 2020), and that this effect is not limited to the soil horizon where the lime had been applied but is also present in deeper soil horizons if lime is leached to such soil volumes. Investigations regarding the tortuosity dynamics of arable land are rarely found and a better understanding of such dynamics would be helpful to adjust the time and intensity of management practices such as liming, aiming to increase the soil aeration and soil fertility.

Material and Methods

Sampling Sites, experimental design, and soil sampling

The soils at the sampling sites located in the marshlands of the federal state Schleswig-Holstein are classified as Haplic Gleysol (IUSS WRB, 2014), or “Kleimarsch” (Ad-hoc-AG Boden, 2005). The sampling sites are representative for the more clayey soils in the district of Dithmarschen (Barlt, 54.028635; 9.087477) and for the siltier soils in the district of North Friesland (Struckum, 54.597971; 8.965612) and are denoted as clay and silt, respectively. Table 1 informs about the soil horizons and the sand, silt, clay, and the soil organic carbon contents, and pH values.

Table 1. Sand, silt, clay, and organic carbon contents and initial pH values of the topsoils (Ap) and subsoils (Go) at the clayey (Barlt) and silty (Struckum) sampling sites.

	Horizon	Depth	Sand	Silt	Clay	SOC	pH
		M	g / kg				-
Clay	Ap	0 - 0.27	100 ± 10	450 ± 30	450 ± 40	34 ± 2	5.5 ± 0.2
	Go	0.27 – 0.95	70 ± 10	560 ± 20	370 ± 20	16 ± 3	5.3 ± 0.2
Silt	Ap	0 – 0.3	160 ± 10	570 ± 20	270 ± 20	15 ± 1	4.7 ± 0.2
	Go	0.3 – 0.7	100 ± 20	700 ± 30	200 ± 30	12 ± 1	5.1 ± 0.2

According to Köppen (2011), the climate is classified as temperate oceanic at both sampling sites with 8.3 °C (clay) and 8.1 °C (silt) mean annual temperature, 801 mm (clay) and 826 mm (silt) precipitation on the average (Fick et al., 2017). The soil management included annual conventional tillage up to a soil depth of 0.3 m, harrow, and mineral nitrogen fertiliser applications (see Figure 1 for the tillage dates).

Fig. 1. Monthly mean temperature (A) and mean precipitation (B) for the clayey and silty sampling sites located in Bartl (solid and blue lines) and Struckum (dashed and orange lines), respectively, during the experiments (2016 to 2018). Vertical lines indicate the date of lime application (solid line) and soil sampling (dashed lines). Symbols indicate the time of soil tillage with a harrow (circles) and with plough (triangles) for the considered sampling sites with black (Bartl) and orange symbols (Struckum).

The crop rotations consisted of winter wheat, winter rapeseed and winter barley for the last decades. Summer crops were sown in case of a weak seed emergence of winter crops. The soils were limed at the beginning of the experiments in October 2016. No lime, and either limestone (CaCO_3) or quicklime (CaO) each in two intensities was applied at the surface layers and incorporated into the Ap horizons (Table 1) by conventional tillage with a mouldboard plough. The lime supply was equal to VDLUFA (2000) recommendations for CaCO_3 (KK-1) and CaO (BK-1) which were 75 dt/ha (clay) and 166.7 dt/ha (silt) for KK-1, and 40 dt/ha (clay) and 88.9 dt/ha (silt) for BK-1, respectively. The recommended lime supply was increased by 50% resulting in 112.5 dt/ha (clay) and 250 dt/ha (silt) for KK-1.5 and 60 dt/ha (clay) and 133.3 dt/ha (silt) for BK-1.5. No lime was supplied to reference plots to document the soil pore tortuosity dynamics without liming (OK). The experiment was designed in randomised blocks with four replicates (i.e., ‘plots’) per treatment at each sampling site. Each plot had a size of 6 m x 18 m. For each lime treatment, sampling site, soil

depth and sampling timepoint, one soil core sample (10 cm in height, and in diameter, i.e., 471 cm³ in volume) was excavated from each of the four plots (i.e., different soil pits). Thus, four soil cores were considered per lime treatment, sampling site, soil depth and sampling timepoint. Sampling took place 7 (T1; April 2017), 12 (T2; August 2017), and 24 (T3; August 2018 for the clayey site) and 26 (T3; October 2018 for the silty site) months after lime application. Disturbed soil materials were taken for texture, pH and soil organic carbon (SOC) content analyses at the beginning of the experiments.

Parameters related to pore capacities and pore function

The soil core samples were water-saturated by capillary rise and then equilibrated to a defined matric potential, ψ_m , equal to -6 kPa on sand beds. Thus, macropores ($\geq 50 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter as described by Jurin's law) became air-filled. The values of the water content, θ , and the air-filled porosity, θ_a , were calculated from the total porosity as determined by thermo-gravimetry after drying at 105 °C for 24 h. The effective soil gas diffusion coefficient (D_s) was determined with a double chamber system as described by Rolston and Moldrup (2002). The upper and lower chambers which enclose the soil sample are either filled with synthetic air (20.95% pO_2) or nitrogen (0% pO_2), respectively. The partial oxygen pressures (pO_2) in both chambers were monitored for a period of four hours (Mordhorst et al., 2017) using oxygen Clarke-type electrodes (OX-100, UNISENSE A/S, Aarhus, Denmark) connected to a 16-bit AD-converter (4 channel Multimeter, UNISENSE A/S, Aarhus, Denmark). The difference in oxygen concentrations (ΔC in g m⁻³) between the two gas-tight chambers were used to calculate the values of D_s according to Uteau et al. (2013):

$$D_s = \frac{-\ln\left(\frac{\Delta C}{2} \cdot C_{eq}\right) \cdot V \cdot L}{A \cdot t^2} \quad (6)$$

with the effective gas diffusion in soil, D_s (m² s⁻¹), the final oxygen concentration at equilibrium, C_{eq} (g m⁻³), the chamber volume, V (m³), the core length, L (m), the soil core surface area, A (m²), and the time from the start of the experiment, t (s).

The oxygen diffusion coefficient in free air ($D_o = 2.01 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) at a given temperature and atmospheric pressure conditions (Gliński and Stepniewski, 1985) was used to calculate the relative diffusion coefficient (D_s/D_o). Prior to measurements, a two-point calibration was applied for oxygen electrodes. The zero point (0 kPa) was obtained by using an anoxic solution (2 g sodium ascorbate diluted in 100 mL of 0.1 M NaOH), while pO_2 equal to 20.95 kPa was assumed for a well-aerated aqueous calibration solution.

Texture, pH, and SOC determination

Disturbed, air-dried soil sieved to pass 2 mm sieves was used for standard soil parameters determination: pH values (25 ml 0.01 M CaCl₂ 1:2.5 m/v, Blume et al., 2010) and soil organic carbon (dry combustion at 1200 °C, Coulomat 702, Ströhlein instruments, Kaarst, Germany; Schlichting et al. 1995). Soil texture was determined by combined sieving and sedimentation

Table 2. Mean values with lower ($C.I._l$) and upper ($C.I._u$) bounds of the 95% confidence interval for the fitting parameter f , and minimum ($\theta_{a,min}$), maximum ($\theta_{a,max}$), and mean values ($\theta_{a,mean}$) of the air-filled porosity, the mean value of the total porosities (θ_s), and of the relative diffusion coefficient (D_s/D_0) with standard deviations (in brackets) for topsoil (0.1 m soil depth) and subsoil (0.3 m soil depth) samples from the soil sampling sites (Site) drained to a soil matric potential of -6 kPa. Degree of freedom, dF , 3.

Site	Depth	Time	Type	f	$C.I._l$	$C.I._u$	$\theta_{a,min}$	$\theta_{a,max}$	$\theta_{a,mean}$	θ_s	D_s/D_0
	m	Month		-							
Clay	0.1	7	0	0.1	-0.12	0.32	0.07	0.11	0.09(0.02)	0.56(0.01)	0.002(0.001)
	0.1	12	0	0.6	-0.01	1.22	0.08	0.11	0.09(0.01)	0.55(0.00)	0.007(0.007)
	0.1	24	0	0.49	-0.01	0.98	0.04	0.16	0.10(0.06)	0.55(0.01)	0.014(0.007)
	0.3	7	0	0.13	-0.04	0.3	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.01)	0.55(0.03)	0.001(0.001)
	0.3	12	0	0.08	-0.02	0.18	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.01)	0.54(0.03)	0.001(0.000)
	0.3	24	0	2.43	0.13	4.73	0.04	0.07	0.06(0.01)	0.53(0.01)	0.012(0.005)
	0.1	7	BK-1	0.35	0.08	0.62	0.08	0.11	0.09(0.02)	0.54(0.02)	0.004(0.004)
	0.1	12	BK-1	1.26	-1.01	3.53	0.07	0.11	0.09(0.02)	0.54(0.01)	0.018(0.018)
	0.1	24	BK-1	0.78	-0.35	1.91	0.08	0.15	0.10(0.03)	0.56(0.03)	0.021(0.003)
	0.3	7	BK-1	0.19	-0.22	0.61	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.02)	0.53(0.02)	0.002(0.002)
	0.3	12	BK-1	0.18	-0.06	0.42	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.01)	0.54(0.02)	0.001(0.001)
	0.3	24	BK-1	1.74	0.26	3.23	0.05	0.09	0.07(0.02)	0.50(0.02)	0.018(0.003)
	0.1	7	BK-1.5	0.3	-0.37	0.97	0.08	0.12	0.10(0.02)	0.52(0.01)	0.006(0.008)
	0.1	12	BK-1.5	2.07	0.96	3.18	0.09	0.12	0.10(0.01)	0.56(0.03)	0.033(0.017)
	0.1	24	BK-1.5	1	-1.12	3.12	0.07	0.14	0.10(0.03)	0.52(0.02)	0.031(0.015)
	0.3	7	BK-1.5	0.43	0.11	0.76	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.02)	0.53(0.04)	0.003(0.003)
	0.3	12	BK-1.5	0.18	-0.13	0.49	0.06	0.09	0.07(0.01)	0.53(0.03)	0.002(0.001)
	0.3	24	BK-1.5	1.98	-0.79	4.74	0.05	0.1	0.07(0.03)	0.51(0.04)	0.022(0.022)
	0.1	7	KK-1	0.25	-0.25	0.75	0.06	0.11	0.09(0.02)	0.55(0.02)	0.003(0.005)
	0.1	12	KK-1	0.56	0.17	0.95	0.06	0.13	0.09(0.03)	0.57(0.02)	0.009(0.005)
	0.1	24	KK-1	0.63	-0.21	1.48	0.11	0.15	0.13(0.02)	0.56(0.03)	0.019(0.010)
	0.3	7	KK-1	0.19	-0.22	0.61	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.02)	0.53(0.02)	0.002(0.002)
	0.3	12	KK-1	0.18	-0.06	0.42	0.05	0.08	0.07(0.01)	0.54(0.02)	0.001(0.001)
	0.3	24	KK-1	1.74	0.26	3.23	0.05	0.09	0.07(0.02)	0.50(0.02)	0.018(0.003)
0.1	7	KK-1.5	0.25	-0.25	0.75	0.06	0.11	0.09(0.02)	0.55(0.02)	0.003(0.005)	
0.1	12	KK-1.5	0.56	0.17	0.95	0.06	0.13	0.09(0.03)	0.57(0.02)	0.009(0.005)	
0.1	24	KK-1.5	0.63	-0.21	1.48	0.11	0.15	0.13(0.02)	0.56(0.03)	0.019(0.010)	
0.3	7	KK-1.5	0.11	0	0.22	0.06	0.09	0.08(0.01)	0.54(0.02)	0.001(0.001)	
0.3	12	KK-1.5	0.17	-0.09	0.42	0.05	0.09	0.07(0.02)	0.51(0.02)	0.002(0.001)	
0.3	24	KK-1.5	3.94	2.75	5.14	0.04	0.08	0.05(0.02)	0.51(0.03)	0.020(0.015)	
Silt	0.1	7	0	0.11	-0.12	0.35	0.1	0.16	0.13(0.02)	0.45(0.02)	0.006(0.006)
	0.1	12	0	0.05	-0.09	0.19	0.11	0.22	0.15(0.05)	0.46(0.04)	0.005(0.005)
	0.1	24	0	0.14	-0.09	0.38	0.06	0.19	0.15(0.06)	0.45(0.02)	0.011(0.010)
	0.3	7	0	0.02	-0.01	0.05	0.08	0.2	0.15(0.05)	0.44(0.02)	0.001(0.002)
	0.3	12	0	0.01	-0.01	0.03	0.06	0.19	0.14(0.06)	0.47(0.03)	0.001(0.000)
	0.3	24	0	0.22	0.15	0.28	0.08	0.16	0.12(0.04)	0.48(0.02)	0.008(0.005)
	0.1	7	BK-1	0.18	-0.04	0.39	0.1	0.16	0.13(0.03)	0.45(0.02)	0.010(0.002)
	0.1	12	BK-1	0.44	0.29	0.59	0.1	0.15	0.11(0.02)	0.47(0.02)	0.013(0.010)
	0.1	24	BK-1	0.42	0.05	0.8	0.11	0.17	0.14(0.02)	0.50(0.03)	0.020(0.007)
	0.3	7	BK-1	0.02	-0.03	0.07	0.16	0.18	0.17(0.01)	0.48(0.03)	0.002(0.002)
	0.3	12	BK-1	0.02	-0.02	0.07	0.08	0.18	0.15(0.05)	0.47(0.03)	0.002(0.001)
	0.3	24	BK-1	0.28	0.17	0.38	0.08	0.18	0.15(0.05)	0.47(0.05)	0.016(0.014)
	0.1	7	BK-1.5	0.5	-0.23	1.23	0.1	0.16	0.13(0.03)	0.46(0.01)	0.024(0.021)
	0.1	12	BK-1.5	0.15	-0.29	0.59	0.08	0.18	0.14(0.05)	0.48(0.01)	0.014(0.009)
	0.1	24	BK-1.5	0.19	-0.36	0.74	0.11	0.22	0.15(0.05)	0.49(0.02)	0.020(0.013)
	0.3	7	BK-1.5	0.04	0.01	0.07	0.08	0.22	0.15(0.06)	0.46(0.04)	0.003(0.003)
	0.3	12	BK-1.5	0.08	-0.04	0.21	0.1	0.17	0.13(0.03)	0.46(0.02)	0.005(0.001)
	0.3	24	BK-1.5	0.51	0.08	0.95	0.08	0.18	0.14(0.04)	0.50(0.02)	0.025(0.013)

Table 2. Continued

	0.1	7	KK-1	0.09	-0.04	0.22	0.08	0.2	0.15(0.05)	0.47(0.03)	0.008(0.004)
	0.1	12	KK-1	0.09	-0.01	0.19	0.1	0.21	0.15(0.05)	0.47(0.02)	0.006(0.001)
	0.1	24	KK-1	0.28	0.1	0.45	0.12	0.21	0.15(0.04)	0.47(0.03)	0.017(0.013)
	0.3	7	KK-1	0.01	-0.02	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.15(0.04)	0.46(0.05)	0.001(0.001)
	0.3	12	KK-1	0.03	0	0.06	0.1	0.21	0.15(0.05)	0.48(0.01)	0.002(0.001)
	0.3	24	KK-1	0.09	-0.01	0.19	0.16	0.2	0.18(0.02)	0.50(0.04)	0.008(0.003)
	0.1	7	KK-1.5	0.12	-0.45	0.69	0.06	0.21	0.13(0.06)	0.48(0.01)	0.015(0.013)
	0.1	12	KK-1.5	0.21	0.05	0.38	0.1	0.16	0.13(0.03)	0.46(0.02)	0.011(0.002)
	0.1	24	KK-1.5	0.42	-0.44	1.28	0.1	0.14	0.11(0.02)	0.47(0.02)	0.016(0.012)
	0.3	7	KK-1.5	0.07	0.01	0.12	0.1	0.14	0.11(0.02)	0.44(0.01)	0.002(0.001)
	0.3	12	KK-1.5	0.04	-0.04	0.12	0.1	0.17	0.13(0.03)	0.45(0.03)	0.003(0.001)
	0.3	24	KK-1.5	0.44	-0.55	1.43	0.1	0.15	0.12(0.02)	0.50(0.01)	0.018(0.014)

processes (pipette method) after removal of cementing substances (HCl to remove CaCO_3 ; H_2O_2 for organic carbon oxidation; Na-pyrophosphate for primary-particle dispersion), according to Schlichting et al. (1995).

Data processing, statistical evaluation, and other used software

The statistical software R (R Development Team, 2022) and the R-implementation of the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (LMA) (Elzhov et al., 2016) were used for data processing and evaluation as described by Haas et al. (2020). Additionally, ggplot2 (Wickham, 2009) was used to visualize the data. For details about the LMA see Lourakis (2005). The LMA started assuming f to equal one. Monthly weather data were taken from CRU-TS 4.05 database (Harris et al., 2014) and downscaled with WorldClim 2.1 (Fick et al., 2017).

Results and Discussion

During the experiments, the rainfall slightly increased, and the temperature decreased (during summer) at the silty sampling site as compared to the clayey sampling site (Fig. 1). The temperature curves showed a pronounced annual variation with minimum temperatures around 0 °C in January and maximum temperatures around 18 to 20 °C in summer. The rainfall in 2016 and 2018 were similar and less compared to the year 2017. The tillage was continued at both sampling sites, whereupon the silty site was ploughed four weeks before the soil sampling campaign at T3 (Fig. 1).

The determined D_s/D_0 (Table 2) values and derived f -values were smaller (Fig. 2A) or higher (Fig. 2B) than the values derived with the Millington-Quirk model (with f equal to 1).

Based on four D_s/D_0 values, the 95% confidence intervals of f are large and even negative values were observed (Fig. 3). The mean values of the linear fitting factor f were increased for soil samples from the clayey as compared to the silty sampling site (Fig. 3). For the topsoil samples at the clayey sampling site, the mean values for f increased continuously with time and CaCO_3 application or were highest at T2 for CaO and without liming (0K). The means were highest at T3 for the corresponding subsoils. At T1, the lowest and highest f -values were 0.013 and 0.500, respectively, indicating more tortuous pore systems than predicted by the MQ model ($f = 1$). The topsoils with CaO application, and with KK-1.5, and

all subsoils developed less tortuous pore systems as predicted by the MQ model (indicated by f -values larger than 1) at least for one of the considered timepoints. Highest f -values were found for the subsoil sample at T3 KK-1.5 > 0K > BK-1.5 > KK-1 > BK-1.0, for each liming intensity and both soil depths.

Fig. 2. Exemplary results of determined $D_s D_0^{-1}$ values (circles) as a function of the air-filled porosity (θ_a) for the clayey subsoil 7 (A) and 24 months (B) after limestone application (KK-1.5) with the MQ model fitted to measured data (dashed line), and the MQ model without fitting (solid line; f equal to 1). $n = 4$. See Table 2 for all data. See also Figs. A1 to A4 (appendix).

Fig. 3. Mean values (symbols) with 95% confidence intervals (error bars) of the linear fitting factor f for the clayey (first three columns) and silty (last three columns) sampling sites as a function of the time after lime application (T1: 7 months; T2: 12 months; T3: 24-26 months) for the topsoils (upper row) and subsoils (lower row) and the liming intensities, i.e., not limed (0K); quicklime (BK) and limestone (KK) application in accordance with VDLUFA recommendations (BK-1 and KK-1, respectively) and 150% of the recommended values (BK-

1.5 and KK-1.5). Note logarithmic scaled Y-axes.

For the silty Haplic Gleysol, all mean values were smaller than 1, with maximum values of around 0.5 for the topsoils with CaO application (T1 for BK-1.5 and 12 months for BK-1) and with KK-1.5 (T3), and for the subsoils with BK-1.5 and KK-1.5 at T3. The mean values of f increased continuously with time for the topsoils with BK-1.5 and KK-1.5. At T3, similar f -values for the topsoil and the subsoil of KK-1.5 were found. For each subsoil, the f -values were in the same order of magnitude at T1 and T2 and increased with T3. For the subsoils and T3, highest f -values were found for BK-1.5 > KK-1.5 > BK-1 > OK > KK-1. For the topsoil of BK-1.5, the f -value was increased with T1, as compared to the values observed with T2 and T3. For topsoil BK-1, the value was in the same order of magnitude with T2 and T3 and increased as compared to the value with T1.

Discussion

In arable soils, anthropogenic soil management practices affect soil structure formation beside natural soil processes such as shrinkage and swelling, plant root growth and exudation as well as bioturbation. Tillage increases the total pore volume in the ploughed soil layer by soil loosening but this status is not persistent and diminishes with time because of the reduced mechanical soil stability (Hartge et al., 2014). In the soil layer located under the ploughed topsoil, platy soil structures are formed which have an increased cohesion and a decreased vertical water and gas transport function (Haas et al., 2016) as a consequence of soil tillage (Horn et al., 1995). Thus, tillage intensely impacts soil structure formation processes in the ploughed topsoil and the subsoil. This dynamic is also reflected by the values of the transport processes defining parameters (e.g., D_s , θ_a and θ_s) and the f -values.

However, the silty site (where only small changes of the f -values were found) had been ploughed less than one month before the soil sampling while for the clayey site this ploughing was more than half a year before sampling. This indicates, that besides soil tillage-induced soil structural changes other processes are reflected by the f -value. A weather effect can be anticipated because of the increased rainfall between T2 and T3 as compared to T1 and T2. This weather effect increases the leaching rates of clay and exchangeable bases such as Ca^{2+} (Webb et al., 1986), and the total mechanical energy supplied by rainfall available for aggregate disruption (splash erosion). Slaking is an aggregate disruptive process and occurs when the aggregate is not strong enough to withstand mechanical stresses produced by splash erosion, swelling, air entrapment and the mechanical action of moving water (Lado et al., 2004; Emerson, 1977). The addition of Ca^{2+} by liming leads to the exchange of dispersive cations such as H^+ and Na^+ from the surface of the negatively charged clay particles. The resulting flocculated particles are arranged in a 'card-house' structure, where clay particles and Ca^{2+} are electrostatically attracted. The pore size distribution of the formed structure changes (Oades, 1984; Holthausen, 2010; Frank, 2020) which increases water infiltration rates and the soil shear strength of such aggregates as compared to the dispersed soil particles (Hartge et al., 1977). Therefore, and based on the increased pH values of the clayey Haplic Gleysol, the rainfall-induced slaking and clay-leaching are expected to be decreased for the clayey as compared to the silty Gleysol. Pores are clogged by clay and SOM (Hallett et al.,

2003) and, thus, reduced slaking and leaching rates result in the preservation of aggregates and connective pores and increased f -values. For the clayey site, root growth is expected to be increased as compared to the silty site due to the increased pH-value which is more favorable for plant growth. Thus, the increased f -values for the clayey as compared to the silty Gleysol may also reflect increased pore volumes formed by plant root growth. The increased f -values at T3 (≥ 24 months after liming), may also be caused by a more intense shrinkage due to an increased evapotranspiration at T3. Shrinkage cracks are formed in vertical (1st crack generation) and horizontal (2nd crack generation) direction when the water menisci-caused tensile stresses are relieved. The resulting cracks act as preferential elongation paths for plant roots (Passioura, 2002) and the formation of connective pores is intensified with increasing root growth, which may even lower the water table at the clayey site more intensely as compared to the silty site.

All these processes perfectly explain the observed patterns of the f -values. Unfortunately, neither soil slaking, clay leaching rates, nor the positions of the water tables were parameterized during the experiments. The generally increased values for the clayey as compared to the silty site are (potentially) caused by more-intense soil aggregation due to Ca^{2+} bridges. Such bridges form, when the negatively charged primary particles electrostatically attract positively charged ions, such as Ca^{2+} holding the particles together (Oades, 1984). Regarding the liming effect, the higher initial pH value at the clayey soil explains the more pronounced changes of the f -values for this site as compared to the silty sampling site. The decreased effect of liming on the f -values at the silty and more acidic sampling site as compared to the clayey site can be explained by the increased fraction of the dispersive cation H^+ at the surface of the clay particles as reflected by the pH-value. The lime is more rapidly neutralized at the silty site, and an increased fraction of dispersive cations are released to the soil solution, as compared to the clayey site where more Ca^{2+} is available. This process may also contribute to the more intense increase of the f -values at the clayey as compared to the silty subsoils because the increased pH-values also reduces the potential leaching of lime and Ca^{2+} to the subsoil. However, separating soil tillage and liming effects and natural crack formation processes (e.g., shrinkage, root growth) is not possible at the current state.

Haas et al. (2019) determined D_s/D_0 values for soil samples from volcanic ash soils influenced by a number of pasture improvement management (PIM) strategies (i.e., varying intensities of tillage and fertilization), and concluded that the soil properties are still in a transition to a new equilibrium, even five years after the PIMs were established. The observed dynamics of the f -values observed here also indicate that a new equilibrium is still not reached. Regarding our own results, this is also reflected in the initial pH values which were increased for the topsoil as compared to the subsoil at the clayey site. Natural soils decalcify from top to subsoil showing a pH gradient with increased values for the subsoil and decreased values for the weathered topsoil. Thus, the soils at the sampling sites are still in transition to a new equilibrium and reaching this new equilibrium is also restricted due to the annual tillage and the coinciding aggregate disruption. Further dynamic changes of the f -values are expected during this transition.

D_s is heterogeneously distributed in soils at the micrometer-scale (Haas et al., 2018), the soil core-scale (Moldrup et al., 2001; Haas et al., 2019; Mordhorst et al., 2017, 2018), and at the soil profile-scale (Kühne et al., 2012; Maier et al., 2017). The coatings of such coarse pores were found to be a function of the origin of such pores, e.g., if the D_s values in radial direction from earthworm burrows and root channels are compared to each other (Haas and Horn, 2018). Concluding that soils with increased values for D_s or f are generally better aerated is critical since further factors such as the number and size of conductive pores also impacts on the aeration of the total soil volume. Additionally, and as shown here, the dynamics of such parameters is huge in agricultural soils, e.g., due to tillage, and typically, the values are parameterized at defined timepoints. In our experiments we did not concentrate on timeseries effects which results in uncertainties regarding the soil structure dynamics and its impact on the f -values. Another uncertainty is the pore continuity and connectivity between the sampled layers. Chamber systems supply a single value for defined soil depths. Usually, the sample is taken in the center of a soil horizon. The connections between the tortuous pore channels at the interface of two soil layers are not considered which are potentially more tortuous and less connected as compared to the pore system within each soil horizon. This reduction occurs naturally in soils with a textural shift at sharp soil horizon borders (Hartge et al., 2014). Additionally, this reduction can be expected when larger soil blocks rotate by conventional tillage, while the internal soil structure of such blocks remained intact (Mordhorst, 2013), and by the formation of platy structures (Horn et al., 1995). Reduced soil oxygen diffusion coefficient for the complete soil profile as compared to the values derived for defined increments of a soil profile is the consequence. Even if the small number of observations reflected by the large confidence intervals is still unsatisfying, the results clearly indicate the dynamics of soil aggregate formation and disruption and the consequence on soil properties describing gas transport processes. The larger the number of observations, the more reliable the fitted f -value. However, we believe that the small number of samples (i.e., four samples per site, depth, timepoint, and lime treatment) does not minder the quality of the presented work which aimed to analyze the spatial and temporal dynamics of the macropore tortuosity. In further investigations, a larger number of soil core samples/observations should be considered. Additionally, the tortuosity can be expected to be a function of the soil matric potential, because coarse macropores such as root channels or earthworm burrows are less tortuous and more connected as compared to interaggregate pores (e.g., fine pores). However, when the f -value is considered for simulations of gas transport processes, or for qualitative soil structure compares (Haas et al., 2020), the matric potentials chosen for parameterization of f should be in the range of expected soil matric potentials.

Conclusion

The presented study shows, that the soil macropore tortuosity as reflected by the f -value is highly dynamic at the time and spatial domains. This is especially true for arable fields, where soil management impacts the soil aggregate development besides natural processes. The f -values were mostly smaller than one, indicating a more-tortuous pore system as predicted by the Millington-Quirk model. The intensity of the soil structural changes and of the f -values are also a function of the initial soil conditions (pH values) and of soil

management practices. All these facts must be considered, e.g., when the gas transport is simulated at the soil profile scale. In further studies, a larger number of soil core samples should be considered to decrease the confidence intervals of the determined f -values. An air-filled pore size-dependent soil pore tortuosity can be parameterized when f -values are determined for soil samples equilibrated to defined soil matric potential steps. This air-filled pore size-dependent soil pore tortuosity may perhaps be helpful to even better understand flow and transport and aggregate formation processes in soils.

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Appendix

A1. Results of the determined $D_s D_o^{-1}$ values (circles) as a function of the air-filled porosity (θ_a) for the clayey topsoil at the three sampling timepoints (columns, T1: 7 months, T2: 12 months, T3: 24 months) for the liming intensities, i.e., not limed (OK), quicklime (BK) and limestone (KK) application in accordance with VDLUFA recommendations (BK-1 and KK-1, respectively) and 150% of the recommended values (BK-1.5 and KK-1.5) with the MQ

model fitted to measured data (blue and dotted line), and the MQ model without fitting (black line; f equal to 1).

A2. Results of the determined $D_s D_0^{-1}$ values (circles) as a function of the air-filled porosity (θ_a) for the clayey subsoil at the three sampling timepoints (columns, T1: 7 months, T2: 12 months, T3: 24 months) for the liming intensities, i.e., not limed (OK), quicklime (BK) and limestone (KK) application in accordance with VDLUFA recommendations (BK-1 and KK-1, respectively) and 150% of the recommended values (BK-1.5 and KK-1.5) with the MQ model fitted to measured data (blue and dotted line), and the MQ model without fitting (black line; f equal to 1).

A3. Results of the determined $D_s D_0^{-1}$ values (circles) as a function of the air-filled porosity (θ_a) for the silty topsoil at the three sampling timepoints (columns, T1: 7 months, T2: 12 months, T3: 26 months) for the liming intensities, i.e., not limed (0K), quicklime (BK) and limestone (KK) application in accordance with VDLUFA recommendations (BK-1 and KK-1, respectively) and 150% of the recommended values (BK-1.5 and KK-1.5) with the MQ model fitted to measured data (blue and dotted line), and the MQ model without fitting (black line; f equal to 1).

A4. Results of the determined $D_s D_o^{-1}$ values (circles) as a function of the air-filled porosity (θ_a) for the silty subsoil at the three sampling timepoints (columns, T1: 7 months, T2: 12 months, T3: 26 months) for the liming intensities, i.e., not limed (OK), quicklime (BK) and limestone (KK) application in accordance with VDLUFA recommendations (BK-1 and KK-1, respectively) and 150% of the recommended values (BK-1.5 and KK-1.5) with the MQ model fitted to measured data (blue and dotted line), and the MQ model without fitting (black line; f equal to 1).